

Qulupunayning O'zbekistondagi navlar va tarqalish hududlari.

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Anotatsiya:Qulupunayning tarqalish hududlari hamda bu rezovor mevaning qanday nomlanishi tug'risida va bu mevaning foydali hususiyatlari va bu mevada uchraydigan vitaminlar tug'risida qisqacha malumotlar.

Kalit so'zlar:Qulupunay mevasining tarkibida 5-11% shakar olma va limon kislatasi, temir moddasi, pektin hamda „A“ „V“ „S“ vitaminlari bor.

Qulupunay mevasi shu turga mansub ko'plab navlarning,avvalo Shimoliy va Janubiy Amerkada o'suvchi F.viriginiana va F.chiloensis navlarning chatishtirilishi oqibatida paydo bulgan reza mevalardan. U ko'plab qulupunaysimon o'simliklar navlarining maxsuli bo'lgani, jumladan bugingi kunda yetishtiriladigan bir qancha navlari mazasi, rangi, meva tugishi xamda xosildorligi bilan bir biridan farqlanishi sababli,u turli iqlim sharoitida issiq tropikdan torib shimoliy xudidlargacha yetishtiriladi. Qulupunayning pishish vaqtiga qarata uni gurihlarga bulib chiqqligan bunda birinchisi.Oddiy qulupunay bulib faqat yoz faslidagina gullashi va bir marta hosil berishi mumkin.Uning har bir tupidan 250-300 gramgacha hosil olishimiz mumkin.

Qulupunay har qanday yerga hamda iqilm sharoitiga moslasha oladi. Qulupunayning yana bir navi bulib bu navning uziga xos xususiyati shundan iboratki,butun yoz buyi xamda kuzning oxirigacha bot bot gullab meva tugayveradi.Remontant qulupunay navining kamchligi shundaki u faqat bir yilgina yaxshi hosil bera oladi keyingi yilda ham hosil beradi ammo keyingi yildagi hosili kichig bulib qoladi shu sababli dehqonlarim eski niholning urniga yangi nihol ekishadilar shunday qilinsa har yili serhosil hamda kuqlab meva beradigan qulupunayni kurishimiz mumkin bu qulupunay kuzgacha gullab pishishi mumkin yaxshi ishlov berilsa hamda ob havo sovuq kelganda qulay muhit yaratilgan taqdirda dekabir oyigacha qulupunay mevasini istemol qilsak buladi.

Qulupnayning erta pishar navi: O'zbekiston" navi mazzali sersuv navi bulib bu navdan 1 kilogramdan 2 kilogramgacha hosil olish mumkin. Bu navdagi qulupnoy 20 maydan 1 iyungacha pishib yetiladi. Keyingisi „Dilbar“ navi bu navdagi qulupnoyning mevasi yirik mazzali bulib bu ham 1,2 kilogramgacha hosil beradi bu qulupnoyning pishish oralig'i 7-10 may oralarida pishib yetiladi.

Qulupnoyning urtapishar navi: Bu navdagi qulupnoylar „Kulver“ „Mayskiy“ „Muto“ navlari bulib quydagi vaqtlarda pisha boshlaydi. Birinchisi „Kulver“ navi bulib bu navdagi qulupnoy mazzali sersuv bulib 1,2 kg hosil olish mumkin. Bu navdagi qulupnoyning niholining tupi urta buyli yoyiq bargalri tuq yashil bulib kasallika va zararkunandalarga chidamli buladi 1-10 iyun oralig'ida pishib yetiladi. Keyingi nav esa „Mayskiy“ navi bulib mazzali hamda dissertbop qulupnoy hisoblanadi. 0,6-1 kg gacha hosil beradi. Kasallik va zararkunandalarga chidamali buladi 10-20 iyun oralig'ida pishib yetiladi. „Muto“ navi esa mazasi birozgina nordonroq 1-1,5 kg gacha hosil beradi. Kasallik va zararkunandalarga chidamliligi urtacha bulib bu ham 10-20 iyun orig'ida pishib yetiladi.

Qulupnoyning kechpishar navlar: bularga „Zenga“ va „Remontant“ navi bulib „Zenga“ mazzasi urtacha 0,9-1 kg gacha hosil berdi. Bu navli qulupnoyni siyrakroq ekish tafsiya etiladi sariq chirish kasaligiga chidamsiz 20-iyundan 1-iyulgacha pishadi. „Remontat“ navi esa mazzali sersuv bulib may oyidan to oktyabr oyigacha hosil beradi. Bu navdan kuzda ikkinchi marta hosil olish mumkin shu sababli ham remontat deb nomlangan. O'zbekistonda hozirgi vaqtda shu navli qulupnoylar ekilib kelinmoqda.

Xulosa: Qulupnoy vitaminga boy rezovor meva hisoblanadi bu meva tarkibida olma va limon kislatasi mavjud hamda „A“, „S“, „V“ vitaminlari mavjud bu mevada ishtaxa ochuvchilik xususiyati mavjud hamda shifobaxsh hisoblanadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Xayitovna, Pirmqulova Muxabbat, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "Cauliflower Growing Technology." *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies* 6 (2022): 8-10.
2. Xayitovna, Pirmqulova Muxabbat, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "KARTOSHKANING TARQALISH HUDUDLARI."
3. "O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI 2.18 (2023): 209-212.
4. Xayitovna, Pirmqulova Muxabbat, Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich, and Jumayev Islom Bobomurod o'g'li. "O'ZBEKISTONNING O'RTA MAVSUMDAGI GULKARAM NAVLARI."

VOLUME-1, ISSUE-5

5. Примкулова, Мухаббат Хайитовна, et al. "МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И БИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАСТЕНИЯ ПАМИДОР, СОПТА." *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI* 2.19 (2023): 69-74.
6. Jumageldiyevna, Gulshan Nurmatova, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "ZARANG (ACER) TURKUMI." *Innovation: The journal of Social Sciences and Researches* 1.6 (2023): 6-11.
7. Qizi, Xushvaqtova Muhliisa Nuriddin, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "Achchiq Bodom Turkumi." *Innovation: The journal of Social Sciences and Researches* 1.6 (2023): 141-149.
8. Jumageldiyevna, Gulshan Nurmatova, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "KIVI O'SIMLIGI HAQIDA." *Innovation: The journal of Social Sciences and Researches* 1.6 (2023): 12-17.
9. Jumageldiyevna, Gulshan Nurmatova, Abdurayimova Mujgona Abdujalilovna, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "QAYRAG 'OCH (ULMUS) TURKUMI." *Innovation: The journal of Social Sciences and Researches* 1.6 (2023): 32-35.
10. Qizi, Jo'Rayeva Go'Zal Davlat, Shaymanov Sherzod Kamol O'G'Li, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "GO 'ZAL KATALPANING MARFOLOGIYASI VA MANZARAVIYLIK XUSUSIYATLARI." *Innovation: The journal of Social Sciences and Researches* 1.6 (2023): 46-49.
11. Qizi, Hamidova Dilrabo Chori, et al. "JASMIN (JASMINUM) TURKUMI." *Innovation: The journal of Social Sciences and Researches* 1.6 (2023): 53-56.
12. Jumageldiyevna, Gulshan Nurmatova, Abdurayimova Mujgona Abdujalilovna, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "PISTA (PISTACIA) TURKUMI." *Innovation: The journal of Social Sciences and Researches* 1.6 (2023): 36-38.
13. Pirmqulova, Muxabbat Xayitovna, et al. "O'ZBEKISTONNING O'RTA MAVSUMDAGI GULKARAM NAVLARI." *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* 3.2 (2023): 661-665.
14. Xayitovna, Pirmqulova Muxabbat, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "Exploiting Seasonal Varieties of Tomato Cultivation for Enhanced Yield and Nutritional Impact in Uzbekistan." *Indonesian Journal of Innovation Studies* 24 (2023): 10-21070.
15. Xudaynazarovna, Ashurova Muxliisa, Muxammadiyeva Gulchiroy Raxmonovna, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "O'G'ITLARNING TURLARI-XUSUSIYATLARI, TUPROQ

STRUKTURASIGA VA O'SIMLIK HOSILIGA TA'SIRI." *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI* 2.18 (2023): 204-208.

16. Faxriddinovich, Mamarajabov Samandarbek, et al. "FERTILE VARIETIES OF GOOSEBERRIES."

17. Faxriddinovich, Mamarajabov Samandarbek. "ZIRK (BERBERIS) TURKUMI." *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI* 2.16 (2023): 690-694.

18. Abdullayev, Muxtorjon, and Samandarbek Mamarajabov. "VARIETIES AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF WHEAT PLANT SELECTION IN UZBEKISTAN." *Евразийский журнал академических исследований* 2.11 (2022): 100-104.

19. Xayitovna, Pirmqulova Muxabbat, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "KARTOSHKANING TARQALISH HUDUDLARI." *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI* 2.18 (2023): 209-212.

20. Xayitovna, Pirmqulova Muxabbat, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "Cauliflower growing technology." *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies* 6 (2022): 8-10.

21. Xayitovna, Pirmqulova Muhabbat, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "Types of corn grown in Uzbekistan and their peculiarities." *Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences* 3 (2022): 59-63.

22. Abdukarimovna, Abdukarimova Mamlakat, Qulmurotova Aziza Muhiddinovna, va Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "POMIDOR ZARARONCHILARI" *Finlyandiya xalqaro ta'lim, ijtimoiy fanlar va amp; Gumanitar fanlar* 11.2 (2023): 427-430.

23. Xolmamatovna, Xafizova Matluba, et al. "TYPES OF SOILS COMMON IN UZBEKISTAN AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS." *American Journal Of Agriculture And Horticulture Innovations* 2.09 (2022): 13-19.

24. Nodirovna, Nabijonova Halima, et al. "Village Farm Plants Pests." *Vital Annex: International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences* 1.5 (2022): 217-220.

25. Xayitovna, Pirmqulova Muxabbat, et al. "Planting Cauliflower Seeds in the Open Field." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF INCLUSIVE AND SUSTAINABLE EDUCATION* 1.5 (2022): 240-246.

26. Faxriddinovich, Mamarajabov Samandarbek, et al. "FERTILE VARIETIES OF GOOSEBERRIES."

VOLUME-1, ISSUE-5

27. Bobirovich, Abdullayev Muxtorjon, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "VARIETIES AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF MOSH PLANT SELECTION IN UZBEKISTAN."

28. Xayitovna, Pirmqulova Muxabbat, and Mamarajabov Samandarbek Faxriddinovich. "BIOLOGICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF POTATOES."

29. Rajametov Sh, Normurodov I, Adilov X, Nomozov I, Meva rezavor meva va tok kuchatzorlarini tashkil etish. O'quv qullanma.Toshkent-2018

30. Zokirova M.S. Axmedova Z.R. Yaxyayeva M.A., Dodayev KO Topinambur (*Heliantus tuberosus* L.) tuganagini saklashning yangi biotexnologik usullari O'zbekistonda yaratilgan topinambur industriyasining salohiyati korporativ innovatsion hamkorlik natijalari va istikbollari T.2013 123-130 bet

31. Abdullayev, Muxtorjon, and Samandarbek Mamarajabov. "VARIETIES AND ACHIEVEMENTS OF WHEAT PLANT SELECTION IN UZBEKISTAN." *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research* 2.11 (2022): 100-104.